

ETERNAL VALUES IN THE PHILOSOPHY OF SWAMI VIVEKANANDA

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Vivekananda stood for all-round freedom – physical, mental and spiritual as well as social and political. He stood also for eternal norms of life which clearly imply a new form of bondage. Sister Nivedita said, “The truth he preaches would have been as true, had he never been born. Nay more, they would have been equally authentic. The difference would have been in their difficulty of access. In their want of modern clearness and incisiveness of statement and in their loss of mutual coherence and unity. Had he not lived texts that today will carry the bread of life to thousands might have remained the obscure dispute of scholars. He taught with Authority and not as one of the pundits. For he had plunged to the depths of the realization which he preached and he came back, like Ramanuja, only to tell its secrets to the pariah, the outcaste and the foreign”!

According to Vivekananda, man is not a puny Creature of blood and bones, he is not merely a volitional Creature either in his real nature he is the king of spirit. Since the essence of spirit is growth, the cult of growth becomes the kernel of his philosophy. For him, growth in the context of struggle, is the sign of life, Individual, social and national as well as international. Therefore, fulfillment of life implies its fullest development. In his view, man is in bondage. His clarion call is for all-round freedom-physical, mental and spiritual as well as social and political. He fully recognized and propagated the eternal axiom that freedom is the condition of securing growth.

Growth must always be from within and according to one’s own law of growth Vivekananda found the so called civilized peoples came to boast much about the progress of civilization. To him, theirs was just a case of making virtue of a necessity. But it was a dangerous practice, since by deceiving others they were also deceiving themselves. Freedom is also necessary to perceive harmony with all other human beings. When one perceives

harmony with all human beings one cannot have any desire to hold others in bondage – Social or Political’. Perception of unity presupposed perception of equality with all members of the species and this cannot be possible without freedom.

Vivekananda seeks to realize fraternity not by asserting rights but by inculcating in the individual a sense of duty and part of his very nature when the individual perceives his duty and performs it in accordance with the dictates of his soul he paves the way for fraternal society. He emphasizes man – making as essentially a problem of becoming theories, education religion these may assist but each individual will have to acquire his freedom – each will have to work out his own salvation. He should have to motto for the propose which Vivekananda sums up in just two words: renunciation and service. Man – making is another name for individual perfection and, therefore, the emphasis in his social theory is upon individuality.

In Vivekananda Philosophy renunciation and service are the convex and concave surface of the same coin. Renunciation his never the end of his ethics. It is just the beginning – it is its open sesame. Renunciation culminates in loving service to fellowmen. It implies giving up attachment to small thing for achieving something great. It is indeed a conquest and in its very nature requires sustained and determined efforts. Absorption in the work undertaken and indifference to everything extraneous to it by such absorption by choosing toil and refusing ease.

He exhorts mankind to the task of building a good society by realizing the eternal qualities like freedom, equality, brotherhood: etc Good society depends upon the principles of right relation of the individual to society. When everyone is by instinct a seeker of happiness, the greatest welfare can be promoted if they come to an agreement and seek the happiness of all. Thus, it is enlightened self interest or unadulterated common sense pure and simple that can determine the principle of proper relation between individual and society and there by promote happiness of man in society.

Vivekananda holds that common sense of reason alone could never be the eternal guarantee of philanthropy. He said “Utilitarian standards cannot explain the ethical relations of men, for We cannot derive any ethical laws from consideration of unity. The utilitarian ask us to take up ethics and good do society..... why should I do good to other men, and not injure them? If happiness is the goal of mankind, why should I not make myself happy and others unhappy? What prevents me? To him, what is needed is a faith – a religion – in addition to reason. It is rational faith alone which can mould ideal social partnership.

Renunciation result in service or rather service is the medium in and through which renunciation manifests itself. Service is never an act of charity; it is pure. Selfless act of love done to others prima facie in disregard of consequences but, in ultimate analysis is for leading them to the road of freedom. Annadana, Vidyadana. Jnanandana and other acts of charity are only means of enabling the man in bondage to secure freedom. The giver himself attains freedom in the process, for thereby he perceives harmony with all things and realizes his truth self. Man is not a solitary animal; he lives moves and has being the social setting and, therefore, for future life he must perceive harmony with his neighbors.

Plato has a parallel concept of renunciation – services. He emphasizes a sense of social duty rather than a struggle for individual rights in his quest of justice, which is synonymous with virtue and goodness. Good society for him rests in a stratified system of social functions under which an individual perceives his duty and performs it in accordance with the dictates of the soul. What Plato prescribes may be described as spiritualization of social relationship which according to Vivekananda should be the basis of and watchword of civilization.

According to Vivekananda religion never consists of dogmas; religions imply the conquering of the inner man, understanding the secrets of the subtle working that are within the human mind, and knowing its wonderful secrets”. And science is, according to him nothing other than “Comprehending the laws that govern the parties of matter outside us.”

Thus, science and religion are never antithetical in nature. They are really complementary. All knowledge is but a part of religion and science is nothing but the finding of utility. This act of proving the unity of science and religion is but a part of his philosophy of assimilation and synthesis. Prof. Ainslie T.E. Embree said, “at a time when some of the strongest voices in India were equating any accommodation with western ideas as an attack on the traditional religious values of India. Vivekananda argued that science was neutral; it could enrich, not weaken Indian life.

According to Marcus Aurelius’s “My city and Country”: So far as I am Rome Antoninoitus, is, but so far as I am a man, it is the world”. We find an echo of this in Vivekananda when he says, I belong to India as much as to the world. Another name of this synthetic outlook is the ideal of the universal man towards which philosophers have been striving since the days of the Stoics and which, according to Vivekananda, is an essential part of India’s message to the world Vivekananda practically identifies the ideal with true Brahminhood. To him the Brahmin does not represent a caste but an ideal – The ideal of spiritual values. A true or an

ideal Brahmin is a man of renunciation and culture. He forsakes small things for attaining to some thing great. To perceive harmony with all other human beings the individual is required to broaden his cultural outlook. This is essentially an aspect of renunciation for it signifies taking leave of all forms of chauvinism and eagerness to understand and appreciate other ways and view of life.

Self respect is essentially a human property; It lies at the base of all religions, all missions and all forms of growth. If it is a sin to lose faith in man, it is a far greater sin to lose faith in one self. Vivekananda passionately preached its inculcation. To be self – respecting, a people like an Individual, must renounce all shades of selfishness.

Vivekananda is in complete agreement with J.S. Mill and others that with small men no greater thing can really be accomplished. Liberty being the first condition of growth what the individual requires for his perfection is all-round freedom. This led him to modify his organic conception of society a little. Although in his view. Society is essentially of organic character, he never seeks to identify the will and personality of the individual with those of all. In his philosophy, society clearly exists for the growth both of the Individual and of its own.

Vivekananda asserts that self promotion must always be “from within” and “according to ones” own law of growth, and that the historically acquired character of a people must be preserved. Society is always under the discipline of a high purpose the purpose of securing the growth of the individual and that of its own and that of its own.

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